

PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION OF ECONOMIC AND LEGAL TEXTS IN THE CONTEXT OF THE FEATURES OF SPECIAL TERMS

Yusupova Sitora Qayum qizi

Uzbekistan State World Languages University

2nd. year Master's student of the

Department of Interpretation.

sitorakhonkayumovna@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

When translating a text of economic or financial nature the translator should be able to process and understand the information to avoid ambiguities in the produced document. It implies an analysis in the contextual area which has a specific mission of confirming the correct meaning of a given term.

Keywords: *economic translation, economic materials, economic documents, grammatical competence, socio-linguistic competence, discourse competence, strategic competence.*

INTRODUCTION

Economic translation is one of the types of special translation. It is based on working with various economic materials. Economic texts logical profile, of course, have their own characteristics factors that significantly affect the process and translation result. First of all, the translation of economic texts is inevitably associated with the analysis of a specific economic system, its essence, content, forms, etc., since the economic text often presents different personal national economic systems that at the same time they are part of one supranational economic system. The difference between economic systems the main problem of translation, in which it is necessary to example, convey European economic realities means of the Russian language.

ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

In terms of adequacy, the completed translation document issued by an international organization should be text that conveys content original document, its semantics, style and format. Legal translator documents of such organizations should take into account the fact that, in particular, the regulatory documents of the European Union. These are EU laws that have direct effect in all countries - members of the EU, and since the economic system of the EU itself is supranational, then its economic legislative acts take precedence over national laws.

Translation of special economic terms poses a number of difficulties. Many terms are from several lexical units, in the translation of which it is necessary not only to correctly decline the noun and form the plural (this, in fact, routine work of a translator), but correctly position elements included in a complex combination. Although knowledge of terminology and not enough to perform translation, however, knowledge of terminology is important role, since the terms define and systematize concepts. They are a kind of keys, organizing structuring, structuring and coding special new information

Experts note that between economic systems there are significant structural differences, Therefore, often economic realities, concepts and models one economic system have no equivalents in another. In addition, there are different conceptual devices used in various economic systems, which creates difficulties for both economists and for translators.

Following are some professional competitions (grammatical, socio-linguistic, discourse and strategic), which must possess Professional translator:

- grammatical competence: knowledge of language norms, vocabulary, rules of word formation, Punctuation and writing, sentence structure;
- socio-linguistic competence: ability understanding and interpret the context conveyed to give the real meaning of the statement;
- discourse competence: the ability to understanding and logically build individual statements;
- strategic competence: communication skills, strategies that provide additional information to the addressee.

As a rule, the main structural elements such legislative documents are: title; preamble, including introductory words, references and constant part; operative part, including general provisions, basic provisions, transitional provisions, other provisions and final provisions. When translating the above documents, the translator should not deviate from the original text, when executing of such a translation, its role is in no way reduced to interpretation.

DISCUSSION

In general, an adequate translation should convey content, style, general message and tone of the original text, however, in order to correctly display the lexical units, phrases and phrases included in the text document, the translator must use the correct forms of the Russian language, its semantics and terminology. But it should be noted that the translation of special texts are subject to additional requirements, i.e. when translating such texts must be strictly observed certain rules, which can be considered as standards. On the one hand, they certainly facilitate the work of a translator, but on

the other hand, they create certain problems. Working with special text, including both terms and general vocabulary, the translator should not only observe morphological, syntactic and lexical norms of the common language, but also take into account norms of a special language, which is intended for expressions of special information, originally calculated on professionals. Special feature language is the presence of many syntagmatic units prostrate and complex terminological constructions that create translation problems.

CONCLUSION

The completed translation must be adequately translated give the content of the original text in compliance with semantic, grammatical, stylistic and orthographic standards. The evolution of political, economic and social relations in the direction of organisation inevitably affects the economic vocabulary. The translator must take into account these changes, which, in ultimately lead to the unification of the economic dictionary. Harmonization of the economic system is mutually mutual agreement, integration into a system, coordination, streamlining and ensuring mutual compliance with economic processes, relations, goods, taxes is an important factor influencing the the work of a translator.

REFERENCES

1. Bell Roger. Translation and Translating: Theory and Practice: Longman. – London and New York, 1991.
2. Glossary on European integration (terms of treaties and agreements of the European Union in English, Russian, French, German and Dutch). - Moscow: "Interdialect +", 1998.
3. Hometkovskaya L.G. Instruments terminologiques informatises: avantages et qualité. In: Collection of articles of scientific session These XIII Neva Readings "Language and Society: Problems, Searches, Solutions". – St. Petersburg: Nevsky Institute language and culture, 2011, pp. 237–247.
4. Newmark P. A Textbook of Translation. – London: Prentice Hall, 1998.